

D4.11 Technical Documentation of R5, R6 and R7: **Apps**

FDEUSTO

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Executive Summary

The current deliverable focuses on the technical details behind the design of the apps (R5-R7).

Section 1 makes an introduction about the concepts behind the R5-R7 eco-solutions. It highlights the domain details and discuss the decisions taken around their design. Section 2 gives an overview of the main functionalities of the apps according to the scope and objectives of Waste4Think. Section 3 describes the integration and communication with the rest of the Waste4Think ecosystem, especially with the ContextBroker. Section 4 details the technologies that will be used for the implementation of the apps in terms of front-end, back-end and continuous testing. Section 5 details the KPIs in terms of waste management and impact of the eco-solution itself that will be measured by the usage of these apps. Section 6 details the approach that ensures the quality of the product through a methodology of continuous delivery and testing procedures. Section 7 and Sections 8 list the main functionalities of the Food App and the Citizen App respectively, describing also the entities for the data model and giving an overview of the mock-ups to better describe how each of them can be used.

1. Introduction

When the waste management term comes up it is easy to think about how much, when, what and where this waste is, even if this generation comes from domestic citizens, schools, or enterprises. In this context, mobile applications (Apps) play an important role as: they will help to exploit all this detailed real-time information from citizens over the different collections systems (Pilots) fostering citizen participation and involvement which is one of the main challenges of the Waste4Think project.

To this end, initially the development of three applications was foreseen:

- The Food App (R5) for edible food waste prevention (R5). With the support of a real-time characterization system, this app will allow citizens and enterprises to advertise the products that continue to be in good condition but are going to be thrown and to implement cost-effective processes for their collection and retrieval by social kitchens, for example. With a prevention approach the app will also give information to the generators (large generators as supermarkets or restaurants, but also citizens in general) about their daily generation patterns.
- The Local Trade app (R6) for fostering sustainable local trade and eco-tourism by:
 - Getting to know the incentives achieved by their behaviour, etc.
 - Getting information about the ways they can get incentives and the offers where they can use them (such as discount vouchers on business).
 - Getting information about the environmental (as the ecological footprint) and social impacts of the products and services that have been used in their neighbourhoods.
 - Getting information about the businesses that have implemented ecological products or services such as the use of good practices on waste prevention (use recyclable bags...).
 - Getting information about the correct way of sorting a product through the QR code of the envelope.
 - Getting to know about the cooperative actions in the municipality such as composting or other decentralized treatment solutions.
 - Sharing and recycling furniture, appliances, clothing, toys, etc
- The Citizen App (R7) to foster transparency and citizen participation by providing interfaces for the components of the system that citizen and enterprise managers will use to get and send information about the state of the collection system. The app will also:
 - Allow consulting the invoices and retrieving information about citizen behaviour as well as the overall state of the waste collection system in the municipality like the economic, environmental and social impacts.
 - Send incidents in the collection spots like overfilled bins, broken infrastructures, etc.
 - Provides tips to improve the way of sorting, reduce the waste generated or information about the clean points.
 - Allow citizens to get access to the bill information or submit issues about the collection system.

However, after consultation with experts and stakeholders, this first approach has been adapted taking into consideration market and usability issues. Therefore, two apps have been envisioned: Food App and Citizen App, the latter as the result of merging Citizen and Local Trade Apps to maximize the impact among residential and non-residential profiles.

In this deliverable, a detailed overview is covered about the technical considerations of the design, development and implementation of these applications, as well as their relationship with other modules and features within the Waste4Think ecosystem. The *Food App* (R5) and *Citizen App* (R6-R7) will represent handy-tools that allow citizens to manage the gathered information, public (from their communities) and private (from themselves), to improve their individual behaviours and as society about waste management and prevention habits, learning how to optimize the sorting rates and optimize the use of resources, sharing their feedbacks with others, helping the improvement of the collection system on the issues reports and as a final purpose taking care of the environment.

Please note this report is also linked with the following deliverables:

- *D1.1 Pilot Planning documentation* for information about the functional requirements of R5-R7 and use cases.
- *D1.2. Best Practices Database in Circular Economy, Economic Instruments and Prevention Actions* for information about the best practices database in circular economy.
- *D1.3 Sustainability Assessment Models* for information about the user requirements, the definition of the criteria to evaluate the sustainability regarding food waste prevention and local trade and the set of the KPIs defined to monitor waste management systems as well as the impact of the use of the Apps.
- From *D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report* to *D1.7 Full Test Report* for details about the progress and time schedule of the development, testing and delivery of the apps.
- *D2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module* for information about the technical details behind digital the architecture of the Waste4Think components.
- *D2.9 Technical Documentation of R4: Circular Economy Planning Module* for information about the module of Circular Economy.
- *D4.2. Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions* for information about the content and methodology behind the implementation of the information featured by the apps.
- *D5.1 Technical Documentation of the Invoicing Module for R2* and *D5.3 New Regulations to Implement PAYT Systems (R16)* for details about the specific of the implementation of the PAYT system in the different pilots.
- *D6.1. Exploitation and IPR report* and *D6.2. Identification of key results and functional analysis of each key result* for information about the exploitation plan for the apps after the end of the projects.

The status of the development for the R4.11 is provided in **the Monitoring Action Reports (Deliverables D1.4 to D1.7).**

2. Functional overview

The *Food App* (R5) and *Citizen App* (R6-R7) are web-based applications that can be accessed from mobile devices (smartphones, iPad/tablets) with Android/iOS and from computers (desktop web browsers). In both cases these applications feature a proper viewport configuration and design focused on an optimal user experience as detailed on Sections 7 and 8.

Every app will have an **About** section with:

- App logo, description and purpose
- Privacy Policy
- Legal Attributions
- Copyright

2.1 Usage

The web-based implementation decision has been taken as a strategic way to focus on the apps usage and functionalities instead of their maintenance in different operating systems (Android, iOS, desktop) which would require a lot of effort in terms of maintenance i.e. if there is a new version of the operating system or some of the native mobile functionalities change. Moreover, a large number of functionalities will feed directly from the information provided directly by the public Observatory described in Deliverable D2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module, therefore a web-based implementation facilitates their integration in a cross-domain application that is available either from PCs (web browsers as usual) and from mobile markets: Google Play Store (Android) and Apple App Store (iOS).

2.2 Scope & Objectives

The main objective of this set of mobile applications (Apps) is to facilitate collaborative tools for citizen empowerment and engagement to move towards more sustainable and inclusive cities. Due to its global accessibility by everyone from everywhere, citizen, commerce and public in general would be interested in this kind of initiatives about using collaborative tools to improve their citizen behaviours with society and environment.

For the purpose of the Waste4Think Project, these Apps are a set of collaborative and informative tools that will provide an active bi-directional communication channel contributing to the following specific objectives (SO) of Waste4Think

SO1. To **reduce the generation of waste** thanks to the implementation of cost-effective prevention campaigns and the promotion of cooperative activities to boost the reuse and more sustainable consumption models.

SO2. To **promote the long-term behavioural changes of waste generators** (citizens and industries) by fostering transparency, citizen empowerment and engagement.

SO4. To **eliminate the primary waste deposited into landfills** and to maximize waste reuse and recycling.

SO5. To **promote the creation of new government and business models** moving towards a circular economy

Waste4Think Apps will allow:

- To prevent food waste opening a channel for food donation and informing about best practices according to the kind of generator
- To access to information about the waste management system in general, and about individual behaviour, in particular
- To provide tips to improve individual behaviour
- To open a channel to share and participate with best practices in circular economy at domestic and local trade levels

Target audience

The target audience of the apps will be:

- Domestic citizens (residential)
- Enterprises/industries (non-residential citizens)
- Educational centres/schools

Language

The apps will be available in English and on the native language of the four pilots:

- Spanish & Euskara – Zamudio (Basque Country, Spain)
- Portuguese – Cascais (Portugal)
- Italian – Seveso (Italy)
- Greek- Halandri (Greece)

Accessibility

Waste4Think apps will be developed including some elements from the *accessibility guidelines* of the WAI initiative¹ to ensure they can be used by everyone regardless of disabilities creating high quality tools with easy and optimal design that provide equal access to participate actively on the waste management.

Figure 1 shows the accessibility functionalities that will be included:

¹ <https://www.w3.org/WAI/>

Perceivable information and user interface	Operable user interface and navigation	Understandable information and user interface	Robust content and reliable interpretation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-text content with text alternatives • Multimedia with captions • Content is presented in different ways • Content easy to see/hear 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App options are available from a keyboard • Content and texts are easy to read and use • Content can be find and accessed easily 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App options are readable and understandable • Content appears/operates in predictable ways • Users are helped to avoid and correct mistakes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App content is compatible with user tools

Figure 1. Accessibility functionalities of the apps.

Content, multimedia & icons

All icons, images, videos, and any content on the design and development of the Food and Citizen Applications will be labelled for commercial use/reuse and modification; in any case, with the Creative Commons license. In that cases when some references are needed to include (links to web, documents, etc.) i.e. as help or additional information, the author will be asked directly about it and the Waste4Think Project will not be responsible for the maintenance of this sources.

2.3 User Stories

Ane is a citizen of Zamudio. She is very concerned with the environment and because of that, she is strongly focused on being as environmentally friendly as she can. For example, Ane makes her own compost in her house, sorts the waste in all the fractions, and tries to buy only in sustainable shops.

a) Citizen & Local Trade App

Ane is planning to throw a big party to celebrate the birth of her first nephew. She plans to invite all her family and friends. She expects to have at least 40 people in her garden. She must buy a lot of things for the party, including the food, the decoration and a present for her nephew. She went to her favourite grocery store where she knows that she will find sustainable products. Unfortunately, the grocery store is closed. Ane does not know of any other grocery store that provides sustainable products, but she knows that the Local Trade app provides this information. Ane opens the app and looks for a grocery store nearby that has the products she needs. She fills in the form with all the products she needs, and the app shows the list of nearby shops. She picks the first one and goes there.

Ane now needs a pergola to give shelter to the guests. Once again, she uses the app to look for a shop that has this type of product, but unfortunately, she does not find any. Ane goes to the hardware store nearby and buys a pergola. While she was shopping there, she realized that the hardware store had opened a repair shop, where they also build furniture with wood from a local and sustainable forest. This information was not in the Local Trade app, so she fills in a form and sends it so that everyone in the community is aware of the existence of this new local and sustainable service. Ane is also part of an NGO that meets every Sunday to

collect plastics from the municipal parks. So, she decides to share this initiative also in the area of new practices in order to look for more volunteers that may join.

Ane's party has already finished. It was quite fun, but now she has a big amount of waste in her house that she does not know how to manage. First, Ane tries to sort all the waste she and her guests have made but holds several doubts with some of the items. There are several packages that she does not know whether they can be thrown to the blue container or to the yellow one. She remembers that the Citizen app has a utility to solve this type of doubts. She opens the app, looks for the specific packaging and sees that, in this case, they should be thrown to the brown container! She was very surprised, but as she is making her own compost, she put this package in her auto composting zone. She has several other doubts that the app can solve easily.

Ane is now happy. She has finally classified all the wastes but has a small problem: her nephew used a large number of nappies while he was there. The app tells Ane that this fraction should not be put in the rest fraction since it is a particular fraction. Ane does not know what to do with it. Nevertheless, the Citizen app has also a tool to locate the nearest point where she can dispose every fraction. She opens the app and looks for the correct deposit point in which to deposit the nappies. She finds one just two blocks away! She is happy that she will be able to clean all the mess made in the party.

But Ane is very curious about this new container for nappies. She wants to know more about it. She knows that the Citizen apps have information about the waste management system, so she opens it and starts browsing. She finds the information she was looking for: in order to improve the sorting rate, the municipality has implemented a PAYT (Pay As You Throw) scheme which is depending on the individual generation of residual waste. So, in order not to punish those families which generate nappies the municipality has decided to collect separately the nappies. This stings her curiosity to know better his behaviour and understand the calculation of his invoice and visits the area called "My behaviour" to know more about that.

Finally, she goes to the nappies container to throw them and she finds the container is broken. Thanks to the App she sends this incident to the waste collector who comes quickly to repair it. As Ane other neighbours have assessed the position of the containers through the App and the manager decides to change also their location to improve their accessibility.

Ane is even happier now as she has realized the positive impact that her efforts have had.

3. Back-End: Integration within the W4T architecture

As previously specified on Deliverable *D2.1. Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module*, the Back-End of the Waste4Think project is defined by three different systems under a wide infrastructure based on FIWARE-LAB technologies: a GitLab development environment, a Back-End management system with the FIWARE technologies and the Front-End systems to monitoring tools.

This architecture allows the development and integration of the *Food App* (R5) and *Citizen App* (R6-R7) as follows:

- using security components for the SSO-Single Sign On across the authentication and authorization systems (login to the private citizen zone for the proper info management)
- collecting all the public/private data (information in real-time and historical) to its visualization/usage (sorting waste searching, waste collection scheduling, PAYT information, dashboard, stats, images, available incentives and best practices, etc.)
- getting context information from the Pilots via public/private APIs subscriptions and RESTful interfaces (FIWARE GE -generic enablers)
- subscribing to the event notifications/alerts (ORION - ContextBroker GE)

Figure 2. Relation of R5-R7 within the overall architecture of Waste4Think.

Figure 2 shows the relationship of the Food App (R5) and Citizen App (R6-R7) with the rest of the components of the Waste4Think architecture.

The Citizen App (R6-R7) will communicate with the ContextBroker (R1) and the Persistence module (R1) to retrieve the information already available about the configuration of the waste management system of the pilot from which the user. This information will vary depending on the pilot from which the user is accessing the app. The data available in the ContextBroker that will be used by the Citizen App is as follows:

- The type of the different fractions that are collected, the wastes that can be gathered by each fraction, the location of the deposit points, etc.
- Data about new campaigns or social actions that are being carried out in the pilot or have already been carried out.
- Data about the nearest deposit points belonging to a certain fraction.
- Data about the state of the waste management system, such as the recycling rate over time, the amount of waste collected, etc.
- Data about the best practices regarding commerce not only by querying but also by subscribing to the notifications.
- The invoice for the user logged into the app not only by querying but also by notification.

The Food App (R5) will communicate with the ContextBroker and the Persistence to retrieve information about food donations nearby. The user could also subscribe to the notifications is a particular donee in the area and publish Food transactions whenever an exchange is made.

More details about the data model of the Citizen App and the Food App can be found in Section 7.2 and Section 7.3, respectively.

The list of functional requirements fulfilled by the components of R5-R7 is detailed in Table 1. More information available in Deliverable 1.1 Pilots preparation.

Table 1. Functional requirements of R5-R7

R5-6-7_FR1	Common functional requirements of the apps
R5-6-7_FR1.1	There are four profiles of users: generator, receptor, public administration, root
R5-6-7_FR1.1.1	The system should be able to use the municipal authentication system
R5-6-7_FR1.1.2	The system should be able to use OpenID authentication system
R5-6-7_FR1.2	Provide aggregated information to R1_FR4.1
R5-6-7_FR1.2.1	Provide aggregated information about the prevention campaigns to the monitoring system (R1_FR4.1)
R5-6-7_FR1.2.2	Provide aggregated information about the use of the app to the monitoring system (R1_FR4.1)
R5_FR1	Coordinate the collection of food for social kitchens to reduce the edible food waste
R5_FR1.2	To characterize the edible food waste (for domestic generators)
R5_FR1.2.1	Identify the generator
R5_FR1.2.2	Identify the place where the surplus is generated
R5_FR1.2.3	Record the time of publication of the surplus alert
R5_FR1.2.4	Assess the quality of the food waste

R5_FR1.2.4.1	Identify the type of food (cereals, roots and tubers, oil crops and pulses, fruits and vegetables, meat, fish or dairy)
R5_FR1.2.4.2	Identify if it was cooked/uncooked
R5_FR1.2.4.3	Identify the type of preservation that the food has had. The process comprising the most important steps from purchasing to handling leftovers (cold chain, food maintenance or cooking time, if applicable).
R5_FR1.2.4.4	Identify the reason for its discarding (overproduction, spoilage, trim waste, sell-by date expired, best before date expired, aesthetic reasons, other)
R5_FR1.2.4.5	Identify other relevant information (organic product)
R5_FR1.3	Provide suggestion of all the actions that can be done with the food waste
R5_FR1.3.1	Send the surplus alert to potential receptors
R5_FR1.3.2	Provide information on the nearest collection point (composting or valorization)
R5_FR1.3.3	Suggest recipes to reuse the food waste
R5_FR1.4	To record the traceability of all the transactions
R5_FR1.5	Analyse the food waste production to give personalized tips for improving the purchase and consumption of food
R6_FR1	To foster local trade, recycling and mutual learning
R6_FR1.3	Provide information about the environmental impact of product and services
R6_FR1.4	Get and send information about the business that have implemented good practices
R6_FR1.5	Provide information about local cooperative actions to prevent the generation of waste
R6_FR1.5.1	Get the localization of the community composting sites
R6_FR1.5.2	Get the localization of the collection of reusable nappies
R6_FR1.5.3	Allow to report new collaborative prevention actions and good practices that are being carried on
R6_FR1.5.4	Provide aggregated information about the participation in cooperative actions to R1_FR4.1

4. Technologies

The following section describes the technologies that are used to the design and develop the *Food App* (R5) and *Citizen App* (R6-R7) to achieve their functionalities.

4.1 Front-End

To implement the GUI- Graphic User Interface of the applications, and packaging up the functionalities (Back-End) to the visual side where users interact with, we use:

- **HTML/HTML5:** Hyper Text Mark-up Language, is the standard language for the web development. We are developing with the newest version HTML5 to use a larger set of elements and technologies according to the app's requirements and modern point of view.

- **CSS/CSS3:** Cascade Style Sheet, is a style language to work on the user interface (GUI) of web applications. We are using its newest version CSS3 which includes new styles to improve borders, shadows, effects and multicolumn layout.
- **Django:** It's a free and open source web framework based on Python to build clean apps under the MVT (Model-View-Template) pattern previously described on the D2.1 document. We are developing with the last version Django 2.1.2
- **Materialize:** It's an open source framework for web responsive design and development based on Google Materialize Design. We are developing with the v1.
- **Ionic:** it's a free and an open source web framework to build mobile apps using HTML, CSS and JavaScript. We are using the Ionic 3.
- **jQuery:** It's an open source JavaScript library that simplifies the client-side scripting of HTML and events handling. We are using jQuery 3.3.1.
- **Charts.js:** It's an open source library to work with JavaScript charts and interactive graphs in a simple way on the responsive development.
- **Leaflet:** It's an easy open source JavaScript library to manage responsive (mobile-friendly and web browsers) interactive OpenStreet maps, easily customizable with CSS3 and GeoJSON.

4.2 BackEnd

To use the logical, core and technology that supports those components from the Waste4Think project architecture that together enable users to interact with the applications, we use:

- **Python:** It's a high-level programming language which allows to work and integrates systems quickly and efficiently. We are using Python 3 with the Django framework.
- **Angular:** it's a platform that makes easy the web development to desktop and mobile devices. We are using Angular 2.6
- **C# .Net:** It's an oriented object programming language under .Net framework to build robust applications. We use the C# .Net 4.7.1
- **Google Cloud Messaging (GCM):** it's a Google service to manage push notifications on Android devices.
- **ORION-FIWARE Datasources / Context:** the datasources module we access through a REST API in JSON format to retrieve all information needed to display on the different app options.
- **GitLab:** is a repository web based on the source management of the app modules we are developing.

4.3 Testing

After the first release of the applications, we use some tools to check if everything goes as expected, from the user perspective and about the functional requirements expectations. To achieve this, we use:

- **Selenium:** it's a software testing type to execute "regression tests". These test cases are done to check if the previous functionalities work fine after new changes included on the apps.
- **Appium:** it's an open source automation framework for use with hybrid and mobile web apps.
- **RedMine / JIRA:** it's an open source tool for issues tracking and management after development. In that way it's easy to follow the progress and solutions of the bugs found on the apps during the testing phase and real usage.
- **WAVE:** it's an open source tool to check through an URL the accessibility data included on the app. It analyses if the web app includes accessibility elements.

Table 2 summarizes the technologies used for the front end, the back end, and the testing for both the Food App and the Citizen App.

Table 2. Front end, back end and testing technologies for the Food App and the Citizen App.

		Food App	Citizen App
Front End	HTML/HTML5	x	x
	CSS/CSS3	x	x
	Django framework 2.1.2		x
	Materialize CSS framework 1		x
	Ionic	x	
	jQuery		x
	Charts.js library		x
	Leaflet maps library		x
		Food App	Citizen App
Back End	Python 3		x
	Angular 2.6	x	
	C# .Net 4.7.1	x	
	Google Cloud Messaging (GCM)		
	ORION -FIWARE Datasources / Context	x	x
	GitLab		
		Food App	Citizen App

Testing	Selenium	x	x
	Appium	x	x
	RedMine / JIRA issues tracker	x	x
	WAVE	x	x

5. Metrics and collected KPIs

The impact of the Apps will be monitored in terms of waste management and in the impact of the eco solution themselves. More details about eco-solutions KPIs can be found in Deliverable D1.3. Sustainability assessment model. In particular, the KPIs that will be monitored thanks to the Apps will be the following ones:

a) Waste Management KPIs

Food App:

- Food waste avoided thanks to the donation of food surpluses (Kg)
- Food waste avoided per donors thanks to the donation of food surpluses (Kg/Nd)
 - Environmental impact of the food waste avoided (LCA)
- Carbon footprint of the food waste avoided (Kg CO₂ eq.)
- Water footprint of the food waste avoided (m³.)
- Nutrition data of the food waste avoided (kcal.)
- Number of exchanges with NGO collecting food waste (Ne).
- Number of donors using the Food App (Nd)
- Number of donees using the Food App (Nde)

Citizen App:

- Number of people saying that have modified their habits
- Level of satisfaction about the waste management systems
- Number of reported incidents
- Number of Zero Waste ecosystems

b) Impact of the eco-solutions

Table 3. Impact of the eco-solutions

		Citizen App	Food App
KPI-T.1	Amount of information retrieved or stored	Number of entries in the databases that could be consulted: ORION / FIWARE Best Practices -DB	Number of food transaction registered (including food offered and transferred)
KPI-T.2	Reliability of the solution	Downtime of the server provided the information (in %)	Downtime of the server provided the information (in %)
KPI-T.3	Time response of the solution	1/10000 times the time (in s) spend answering a benchmark test-suite of queries composed of: 10000 non-bota-zer queries, 10000 best practice queries and 10000 my generation queries	1/10000 times the time (in s) to register 10000 transactions
KPI-T.4	Quality of the results produced by the eco-solution	--	Kilograms of food donee
KPI-S.1	Number of users	Number of downloads of the app	Number of downloads of the app
KPI-S.2	Amount of use	Number of queries answered	Number of queries answered
KPI-S.3	Satisfaction with the solution	Mean rate of the app in google play and iOS marketplace (likert)	Mean rate of the app in google play and iOS marketplace (likert)
KPI-C.2	ROI (Return on Investment) at year 2 & 5		
KPI-C.3	Payback year		
KPI-C.4	CAPEX		
KPI-C.5	OPEX		
KPI-C.6	Incomes forecast at year 2 & 5		
KPI-C.7	Break-even point		
KPI-E.1	Energy and raw materials consumption on use phase	Energy consumption (in kWh) of a development platform answering the benchmark test-suite developed for KPI-T.3	1/10000 times the energy consumption (in kWh) of a development platform registering 10000 transactions

6. Delivery and Testing

The Food App and Citizen App are developed under an Agile methodology (already specified on the Deliverable 2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module) which allows all the project levels involved to check, analyse and perform a proper evaluation of the current status and details whenever needed about the

1. **design:** definition of the layout, structures, components, workflows and functional - technical details of the application.
2. **development:** tasks/functionalities of the app translated to language programming.
3. **testing:** design, development and execution of test scenarios (natural happy-roads and wrong values intentionally tested) needed to check the expected results and issues (bugs) found during tests execution. These testing tasks are performed during every sprint (app version release -phase) and are detailed in Table 4.

Table 4. Test driven development for the Citizen App and the Food App.

Testing type	designer developer	QA team	new tester	user candidate	testing tool	all
Functional test to ensure the app works as described with the project objectives and functional requirements <i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected behaviour	X	X		X	X	
Usability test to ensure the app is user friendly and intuitive.	X	X	X	X		
Disabilities test to verify if the app can be used by everyone regardless of disabilities <i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected behaviour	X	X		X	X	
Performance test measure how app works i.e. showing the dashboard info <i>input:</i> -test scenarios -expected performance (response time)	X	X			X	
Regression test	X	X		X	X	

to check if the previous tasks are still working as expected after a new app version release

input:
-test scenarios
-expected behaviour

Device test

to ensure the app works properly on a wide set of mobile devices (screens sizes) and operating systems (android, iOS, Windows, Linux)

X X X X X X

input:
-test scenarios
-expected behaviour

Focus group test

a group of new testers (1st time using the app) run test scenarios and QA collect the feedback about how they use the app, what kind of issues they find and their frustrations on its usage

X X

input:
-test scenarios
-expected results

Beta version test

to see how the app performance is on different devices, locations, operating systems, and network conditions

X X X X X X

All testing scenarios will be well documented in terms of design and execution by designers, developers and QA/Quality Assurance Team, including the results obtained after each one. A good approach can be, web-forms to collect involved data and exploit from the first to the last testing scenarios versions.

- bug fixing:** solution to the issues found during the testing phase, including new development and/or improving the existing one.

Both applications, Food App and Citizen App, include these phases with time duration details (specified on the Apps **Gantt diagram** in Deliverable D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report) according with the task priorities, their functionalities meaning (app-option) and project strategy considerations. This Gantt is periodically revised according to the status of the project in the monitoring reports from D1.5 to D1.7.

Finally, information about how the apps will be maintained after the end of the project is available on Deliverable 6.2. Identification of key results and functional analysis of each key result.

7. Food App

The Food App, available for iOS and Android devices, is an application where food waste generators can donate their surpluses (edible food) to people or institutions who pick it up and consume it. On the other hand, generators will receive useful information about their production habits which will allow them to identify and put into practice suitable prevention initiatives according to their generation profiles.

The food donation model which includes the information to be retrieved about donees and food surplus as well as the KPIs to be calculated by the App are explained in Deliverable D1.3 Sustainability Assessment Model.

Users within the app can play two different roles:

- donors, that publish surpluses and
- donees, that browse and request surpluses

The main functionality of the app is to allow donors and donees to carry out the transaction of food donation. This section includes screenshots of the different steps of both the user management process and the food transaction. The pieces of information in these screenshots have been selected and disposed by the criteria of user experience optimization.

7.1 Main functionalities

The main functionalities of the Food App are detailed below:

a) User account management

User authentication through **email** and **password** could be enough, however if we want to uniquely link users and citizens, we need to rely on an external system operated by a public administration (i.e.: Municipality).

The operative of the app is focused on companies and entities, this app is not available for individual peoples. Concerning user info, we need a “CIF/VAT” number to link with real entities and companies and “NACE codes” for statistical purposes. Typical password management screens are also included (both for recover and for change it).

It is important to highlight that the Food App will not maintain any database with information about the user. The responsible for maintaining this information will be the corresponding entities within each of the pilots (i.e. the public administration in the case of the Zamudio pilot). It is responsibility of each pilot to maintain the database and provide the citizens with the means necessary to provide the necessary credential to log into the app (whether the number of the citizen card, a social security number, etc).

New users will not be allowed automatically. They must contact the entity responsible for receiving the credentials.

Figure 3. Screen for creation of account and login onto the Food App.

a) Publishing of surpluses

Surplus generators publish offers through an **add form**. This form must be as simple as possible, but also some mandatory info should be provided to make transactions possible.

The form will be focused on information that donees need to decide if the offer is interesting or not for them. The form will also ask for some information to provide food security. Lastly, some extra info about donors will be collected, to help generator to reduce food waste. Thus, the first step will be the publication of the surpluses by the donor, where it is necessary to take a picture thanks to the use of the Food App using the option titled “Add surplus” (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Example of the “Add Surplus” option used by the donor.

The donor subsequently will enter additional information from these surpluses using the same option called “Add Surplus”. This information is related to the generation date, the place where the surplus is stored, the type of food (cooked or uncooked), pick up deadline, etc (Figure 5). An alternative option to filling in the information manually (photo and weight) would be to use the Kitchen Data App or the DIY kit (see Deliverable D2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module, Annex G). These tools are conceived to help great food generators and individual citizens respectively to help input information into the Food App.

After the donor is done entering all the information, the donor will be informed through warning messages about recommendations for donation conditions according to Regulation (EC) No 852/2004² on the hygiene of foodstuffs as well as considerations published by other local, and regional donation protocols. Some good examples are those published by Agencia Catalana de Seguridad Alimentaria³ or the proposal from

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM%3Af84001>

³

http://www20.gencat.cat/docs/arc/Home/Ambits%20dactuacio/Prevencio/Malbaratament%20alimentari/Publicacions%20especificques/acsa_malbaratament.pdf

Figure 5. Form for the publication of a food surplus.

Caritas Italiana and Fondazione Banco Alimentare⁴. These messages should make clear that the following SHOULD NOT be donated:

- Raw fish and shellfish no properly packed.
- Raw meat and derivatives no properly packed.
- Sweet and/or savoury baked products filled with unpasteurised egg-based custards or sauces.
- Cooked meals with no sauce (grilled steak, dry rice, etc.) because the difficulty of maintaining a constant temperature of 65°C

The donor will be also helped with messages to ensure the correct hygiene practice assuring food safety. These messages will distinguish:

- Non-cooked food: vegetables, fruits, etc.
- Cooked meals: cold and hot meals

The former will be advised to pack and label correctly the food including the recollection date. The later will include recommendations to follow correctly the temperature chain:

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/fw_library_guide-good-practice-english_2016.pdf

Figure 6. Examples of list and detail of surpluses available in the donee profiles.

- Cold meals should be correctly packed maintaining a temperature below 4°C.
- Hot meals should be donated over 65°C ensuring this temperature until the consumption moment.

Notice that donor keeps the responsibility of ensuring correct conditions until the delivery of the meal or food. Please see Regulation (EC) No 852/2004⁵ on the hygiene of foodstuffs for further information as well as labelling conditions. Donors and donees will be informed about the requirement to consume the cooked food in 24 hours. This timing would be increased if using a blast chiller (5 days) or specifically certified refrigerators (3 months).

b) Food transaction

Once the surplus information has been entered by the donor, the surplus will be published in the Food App for the potential donees.

In fact, the main view of the app at the beginning, for the donee point of view, is a list of available surpluses. Basically, it is a **list of resources** (picture, title and some other relevant details) with “call to action” buttons. This listing can be enriched with filters, geo-position and so on.

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM%3Af84001>

Only minimum information should be displayed. This screen is for the user to make a choice between available surpluses. Later, during the transaction, user will get detailed information to confirm the interest.

From the donee point of view, the transaction consists of several steps. When the user is interested in a surplus:

- first, the user will **get detailed info of the surplus**
- **donor information** will be also available (contact info, users' feedback, etc.)
- lastly, **some disclaimers and extra info** will be presented, just before the user confirms his/her interest.

The screens at the donor side are shown on Figure 6. In this step, the donor can assign the surplus to the most suitable donee. For example, the donor could assign this surplus in terms of the proximity with him/her

When a surplus is assigned to the requester, the transaction is ready to be performed physically. Being the donor the one starting the transaction operation, he/she is responsible for setting up the circumstances of the exchange (contact way, time, etc.) A random **secret password** is shared between donor and donee (Figure 8). Users can use this code for their security.

Figure 7. Example of a request of surpluses sent to the donor.

Once the surplus is exchanged, the donor must change the **status of the transaction** to “closed”.

Both recipients and donors have then the opportunity to introduce **feedback**. This feedback can be a public or private and the format as well could be free style comments or closed answers. Public comments will be available in the user’s profiles. Private comments will be only for developing purposes to improve the user experience. Closed answers (surveys) could be automatically computed to feed the algorithms that matches donors and donees.

Furthermore, the donee will be advised to take special considerations in the case of being allergic or suffer from alimentary intolerances.

Figure 8. Example of a confirmation of the surplus request sent to the donor.

On the other hand, the App will provide give feedback about the generation patterns and their environmental impact to the donors making them aware about the impact of the donation. According to the NACE code of the donor, some recommendations will be provided in line with Best Practices recognised by the EC (Deliverable 1.2 Best Practices Database in Circular Economy, Economic Instruments and Prevention Actions).

7.2 Data model

The data model of the Food App relies on two entities to describe the user interaction, one for describing the activity of the user, and another for describing the food transactions.

- **FoodAppUser:** This entity describes the user registered in the food app whether donor or donee:
 - id: Entity's unique identifier.
 - type: It must be `FoodAppUser`.
 - 'family': 'Agent'
 - refResourceSurplus: List of surpluses that are published by the user. This list changes dynamically according to the transactions (donations performed) and the publication of new. Each surplus will feature the following attributes:
 - foodCategory
 - weight
 - weightUnit
 - metadata with additional information about the food surplus
- **FoodAppTransaction:** This entity describes the process of the donation of food between donor and donee:
 - id: Entity's unique identifier.
 - type: It must be 'FoodAppTransaction'.
 - family: It must be 'Transaction',
 - refEmitter: Id of the FoodAppUser that has published the surplus
 - refReceiver: Id of the FoodAppUser that received the surplus
 - refCapturer: Application that captures the transaction. Must be 'FoodApp',
 - date: Date of the transaction,
 - emittedResources: List of surpluses that were emitted on this transaction by the donor. Each surplus will feature the following attributes:
 - foodCategory
 - weight
 - weightUnit
 - metadata with additional information about the food surplus
 - receivedResources: List of surpluses that were given on this transaction to the donor. Each surplus will feature the following attributes:
 - foodCategory
 - weight
 - weightUnit
 - metadata with additional information about the food surplus

7.3 Terms of Use

A special clause for the user to accept (explicitly) the Terms and Conditions of use for the app will be included, following the current regulations on this matter. It will be based on the example provided in Annex A, which is based on the conditions of the Waste App from the Urban Waste project GA No. 690452.

Due to its nature (manage food exchanges), the Food App will include a special clause to inform the users the App is not responsible of the veracity of the information shown (ingredients of the meals –allergens-, expiration date, etc.)

These issues are under review of Waste4Think Ethical Committee.

8. Citizen App

The purpose of the *Citizen App* (R6-R7) is to facilitate and foster waste sorting management on the everyday life as well as to promote more sustainable production and consumption models among citizens (residential and non-residential) over on the four pilots of the Waste4Think project.

8.1 Main functionalities

Figure 9 shows an overview of the main functionalities that will be included in the Citizen App.

	user account management	incentives management	waste management	best practices management	profile management
<p>Citizen (domestic / residential)</p>	<p>View citizen/user account info</p> <p>?update some user data?</p> <p>Language: user device language identification / set a custom language</p> <p>Location current user location</p> <p>Set notifications</p>	<p>View incentives available/achieved (discounts, offers) according by the citizen behavior</p> <p>Update where/when can the citizen use his incentives</p>	<p>View (search) where does the waste go [<i>non-botazer</i>]</p> <p>Update set my waste up (update waste sorting info)</p> <p>View deposit/clean points (details, map, reviews, ...)</p> <p>Report an issue: what's wrong with the collection spot/system</p>	<p>View best practices list (customized to the citizen's behavior)</p> <p>View/make a review about a commerce and its best practices</p> <p>Share a best practice/tip about improving the waste reduction</p> <p>View / share green points (details, maps, reviews)</p>	<p>View My Behavior (billing information)</p> <p>Send a suggestion / contact Support (Tell us!)</p> <p>Like it or not! ?: user review/opinion about other users inputs</p>
	<p>Commerce (non-residential)</p>	<p>View commerce/user account info</p> <p>?update some user data?</p> <p>Language: user device language identification / set a custom language</p> <p>Location: get commerce location</p> <p>Set notifications</p>	<p>View incentives offered by commerce (discounts, offers)</p> <p>Create a new incentive add data, conditions, ...</p> <p>Update an incentive (data, conditions, enable/disable availability...)</p>	<p>View (search) where does the waste go [<i>non-botazer</i>]</p> <p>Update set my waste up (update waste sorting info)</p> <p>View deposit/clean points (details, map, reviews, ...)</p> <p>Report an issue: what's wrong with the collection spot/system</p>	<p>View best practices list (customized to the citizen's behavior)</p> <p>View/make a review about a commerce and its best practices</p> <p>Share a best practice/tip about improving the waste reduction</p> <p>View / share green points (details, maps, reviews)</p>

Figure 9. Functionalities of the Citizen App.

b) User account management

Citizens can manage their user account information, set a profile picture and customize the application settings to their liking, such as:

- **Language & Location:** allows the user to set the preferred language for the application. By default, the app will be in English. Available languages are provided according to the native languages of the pilots (see Section 2).
- **Notifications:** the user can manage its preferences about the frequency of notifications.

- **Login and password:** manage the private side of the application. This will be necessary when the displayed information contains sensitive data with respect to the user of the app.

c) Profile management

Provides a space where the citizen can get information about the waste management system in the pilot through:

- **Dashboard:** being the landing screen of the Citizen App, it includes little pieces of information (widgets) about every section of the application. More details about the content of the Dashboard on Section 8.3.1.
- **My Behaviour:** provides a space where the citizens can compare how they are doing in terms of waste management against the average behaviour of the citizens of the pilot. This will help evaluate individual behaviours like, for example, the evolution of the amount of plastic sorted during a specific period. Since the information shown in this section is of private nature, it would require prior authentication.

d) Waste management

This is the core of the Citizen App. From this section the user can consult when, where and how waste can be sorted.

- **Sort my Waste / non-bota-zer:** this search tool provides guidance about when, where and how a waste can be sorted in an optimal way according to the user input. The result of this search includes a list of deposit points where the waste sorting can be done.
- **Find a Clean Point:** shows up a list of deposit points, collection centres, fixed/mobile collection points, etc. where waste can be sorted according to its category or sorting type. By default, this functionality shows those points nearest to the user location. Other types of visualization can be customized by setting filtering options.
- **My behaviour:** this will be meaningful to get the info about how much the user will pay according to the PAYT scheme implemented in his/her municipality. More information about PAYT in the pilot sites of Waste4think can be found in Deliverables D5.1 Technical Documentation of the Invoicing Module for R2 and D5.3 New Regulations to Implement PAYT Systems (R16). Since the information shown in this section is of private nature, it would require prior authentication

e) Incentives management

A set of campaigns and ongoing cooperatives actions are available in the neighbourhood. These incentives are listed according to the user location. Other kinds of visualization can be customized after filter options are set.

f) Best practices

Provides customized information about social actions organized in their community to improve behaviour and foster awareness on waste reduction and prevention.

- **Best practices for me:** list of ecological products and sustainable services that might be useful for improving the behaviour of the user using best practices on waste prevention. By default, all best practices are listed but this list can be customized according to filters defined by the user.
- **Green Points:** shows up a list of green points such as food banks, composting plants, etc. where citizens can go according to its purpose. By default, it shows up those green points near the user location. Other kind of visualization can be customized after filter options are set.

8.2 Data model

The FIWARE Waste Data model includes characterizations that allow a fine-grained definition of how wastes are grouped and managed in different scenarios, providing a lot of universal cases/scenarios useful for the app's consumption considered on the Waste4Think project as follows:

- The sorting type characterization different countries: waste materials and categories
- A different waste collection system information: time scheduling, street / buried containers, door2door collection, deposit areas, clean points, industrial waste management using specialized deposit points, etc.
- PAYT info: rates for the waste collection services
- Social actions information: management in the different Pilots

Specifically, the Citizen App (R6-R7) use the following Entities and attributes, for each functionality:

a) Profile management

- **Dashboard:** Resource, ResourceCategory, Waste, SortingType, BestPractice
- **My Behaviour:** Invoice

b) Waste Management

- **Sort my Waste** (non-bota-zer): Waste, WasteCategory, SortingType
- **Available Deposit Points:** DepositPoint, DepositPointType, DepositPointIsle
- **Deposit Point details:** DepositPoint, DepositPointType, DepositPointIsle
- **Find a Clean Point:** DepositPoint, DepositPointType

c) Incentives: Strategy, Action

d) Best practices

- **Best Practices for me:** BestPractice, Strategy, Action
- **Green Points:** DepositPoint, DepositPointType, DepositPointIsle
- **Green Point details:** DepositPoint, DepositPointType, DepositPointIsle

e) KPI: KeyPerformanceIndicator

8.3 Front-End design

With a full responsive user interface (adaptable for different devices / screen sizes), the Citizen App is designed for an optimal user experience. This section describes all elements considered to achieve it.

The **Citizen App** can be used in two modes: public and private. This criterion takes effect with the functionality (available app-option) according to the privacy management required. Table 5 summarizes this treatment:

Table 5. Functionality availability in public and private mode.

Functionality (app-option)	Public side	Private side
Login / logout		x
Password recovery		x
Top menu (navbar)	x	x
Top global search	x	x
Left menu	x	x
Right menu	x	x
Dashboard (Home)	x *	x
User account management		x
Language & location	x	
Notifications	x	x
Waste Management	x	x
Sort my waste	x	x
Find a Clean Point	x	x
My Behaviour		x
Available Deposit Points	x	x
Deposit Points details	x	x
Deposit Point directions	x	x
Deposit Point review	x	x
Filtering options	x	x

Incentives	x?	x
Best Practices	x	x
Green Points	x?	x
Citizen survey	x?	x
Shortcuts	x	x
Tell us	x	x
Games	x	x
About	x	x

[*] widgets with sensitive data are only available on the private side (i.e. My Behaviour)

a) External layout

On the private side: when the user runs the Citizen App, the first screen showed up is the **Login screen** for the user authentication which allows the user to access to his/her private information (Figure 10. Login screen layout).

Figure 10. Login screen layout.

The login screen (external layout) includes the following sections:

- **Dynamic image slider:** At the top of the screen, this section is designed to promote local interests with attractive images. Every Pilot can use it to highlight any matter (ongoing initiatives, campaigns, etc.) according to their own strategy.

- **App logo and slogan:** includes the logo of the Citizen App and a small text as a slogan of the application describing what does the purpose of the app is
- **Required data to login:** in the middle of the screen this section contains those fields required for the user authentication such as username and password.
- **Login options:** includes the buttons enabled to execute the login process, i.e. Login and a “Remember me” checkbox option to remember the basic data for the login.
- **Password recovery:** is a link to a recovery password screen where the user should specify an email address to follow the required steps to change his/her password.

b) Internal layout

On the public and private side (both): when the user opens the Citizen App, and/or the login process is completed (private cases) the first screen displayed will be the **Dashboard** with a layout as shown on Figure 12. Dashboard layout.

Figure 11. Internal screen layout.

This layout features three well-defined areas as see on Figure 11:

- **top left side area:** with the left-menu access and the logo of the Citizen App
- **top right-side area:** with the main shortcuts and right-menu access
- **main area:** where all content will be displayed. It's the main section all over the Citizen App. Has been full-width designed to include the information needed for an optimal user experience and will always display the icon of the current option where the user is, i.e.: Waste Management if the user is on the Waste Management screen

Figure 12. Dashboard layout.

c) Main menu and shortcuts

There are some elements that ease the access to the different options of the application:

 Left-menu: this is the main menu of the Citizen App. When the user clicks on this icon, the left-menu opens showing up the following options (see Figure 13. Left-side menu.):

- **User management:** full name + user picture + user credentials
- **Dashboard:** redirects to the Dashboard screen
- **Waste management:** redirects the Waste Management options
- **Incentives:** redirects to the incentives screen
- **Best Practices:** redirects to the Best Practices options
- **Tell us:** redirects to the Contact/Support section of the app
- **Shortcuts:** includes the shortcuts to the options specified by the user (Figure 14. Shortcuts submenu.)
- **Games:** redirects to the Games screen
- **About:** redirects to the About screen that contains information about the Privacy Policy, Legal, Attributions of the Citizen App
- **Logout:** allows the user logout from the application
- **Last sync at:** show the date and time the information of the app was last updates

Figure 13. Left-side menu.

Figure 14. Shortcuts submenu.

WASTE 4think app logo: is the Citizen App logo. It can be used as a shortcut to the Dashboard/Home when the user clicks on it. Currently, we are working on the real logo for the application, for reference purposes we include the Waste4Think logo.

Right-menu: this is the secondary menu of the Citizen App. When the user clicks on it, the right-menu opens and shows the following options available from any screen (Figure 15):

- **Filters:** shows the filtering options for the info/search result displayed
- **Sort by:** allows the user to sort the information displayed (ascending / descending) alphabetically
- **View options:** allows the user to show the information in a thumbnail view or by list
- **Sync:** updates the last date/time info (last update)
- **Tell us:** takes to the Contact/Support section of the app
- **Add to shortcuts:** allows the user to add the current screen to the “Shortcuts” section on the left-menu.

Figure 15. Right-side menu.

Main shortcuts: these are useful options always visible at the right top navbar section of the screen which includes:

search: when the user clicks on it the search box appears and he/she can make a global search all over the app content. See Section 8.3.6 for details.

dashboard: takes the user to the Dashboard screen (see more details on Section 8.3.1)

notifications: when the user clicks on it the Notifications screen is showed up (see more details on Section 8.3.10)

8.3.1 Dashboard

The **Dashboard** screen, also called “**Home**”, is the first screen that appears when the Citizen App starts (Figure 16). The user can access it by using the home icon on the top navbar section, from the app logo or from the Dashboard option on the left menu.

Figure 16. Dashboard screen.

As described in a previous section, the Dashboard provides some pieces of information (widgets) where the user can get an overview of the whole information provided in the Citizen App. Every widget is clickable, and the user can check all details about it from its specific screen option. For example: if the user clicks on the widget “My waste sorting today”, the Waste Management section will be displayed.

8.3.2 Sort my Waste (non-bota-zer)

When the user clicks on the Waste Management option from the left-menu, it shows the following options (Figure 17):

- **Containers:** all deposit points (containers) according to the colour of its sorting type (i.e. yellow for packing, green for glass, orange for oil waste, etc.). These containers can hold digits to represent a relevant information about it, i.e. how many times the citizen has opened this container, or how much this kind of resource has been collected. This usage will be specified later.
- **Sort my waste (non-bota-zer):** an easy search-tool to know where the waste goes
- **Find a Clean Point:** to search the location of the recollection centres, deposit points where to trash uncommon waste (batteries, big stuff, etc.)
- **Check Observatory:** similar to the dashboard section, this will contain waste management information through widgets like where will be the next collection service (truck), etc.
- **My Behaviour:** provides all the payment information generated by the waste management the citizen does (how much they will pay for).
- On the right bottom side of the screen, the that represents this screen it is currently a shortcut entry. This shortcut option is also available from the right-menu previously described. If an option is selected, the application will be highlighted with a light grey area as shown in Figure 17.

When the user clicks on the **Sort my Waste** option (*non-bota-zer* in Euskara translate) it shows a list of available deposit points where the citizen can sort their waste This list is shown according to the current user location (geo-positioning coordinates) which are accessed by the application from GPS, Wi-Fi and mobile networks settings.

Figure 17. Waste Management options.

Sort my Waste represent the core option of the Citizen App which includes:

- **search tool:** a predictive and instant search tool where the user specifies the resource (waste) they need to sort. It will display the result (text and image) while the user is typing (Figure 19).
- **sorting details:** represents the result after the user searches something (Figure 20).
- **available deposit points:** shows a list of available deposit points where the citizen can sort his/her waste (Figure 18).
- **deposit point details:** after the user clicks on the icon the deposit point information (name, address, directions, website, contact number, customers reviews, etc.) is displayed (Figure 21).

Figure 18. Sort my waste: default view of available deposit points.

The available deposit points are shown with a colour tag glass according to their colour container (sorting type) and include a brief information about their location, like postal code and region. The map locates the deposit points by using container icons . The containers on the map can be clicked and the app will show a brief info about it. Also, there are some options to display the information needed:

- **view options:** to change how the info is displayed (list, thumbnails)
- **filter by:** to set all the options to display only that results where the user is interested in
- **order by:** to change the information order alphabetically (ascending, descending)

Figure 19. Sort my waste -instant/predictive search

While the user is typing the application provides all terms that match with their input, i.e. if "pl" is specified the app will suggest "Apple" as the right term (waste) to sort.

If "Apple" is the right search the user needs, the application will show the details about its sort as shown on Figure 20. The app will show:

- an image of the resource (waste to sort), the Apple in this case
- basic information about it: product, category, etc.
- the right container where the citizen must sort it (colour tag and container)
- the deposit point options (location) where this waste can be sorted (a list and a general map with all options)
- a little map for one deposit point option with a button to get the directions to it

Figure 20. Sort my waste -sorting details

In addition to the sorting details the application can show a “Tip message” to invite the citizen to take a complementary action about sorting something, a Tea Bag, for example, would be “Remember to remove the staple and card from the tea bag” (see Figure 21):

This *tip message*, the waste container (image, icons on the map) and the tag colour will be shown in the colour of the container the waste must be sorted.

Figure 21. Sort my waste -Tip message.

Sort my waste -many options

There are some cases when a waste can be sorted in many ways, for example, a tablecloth. If the tablecloth is clean, then the app will suggest sorting it out on the blue container, but what happens if the citizen will sort a tablecloth with other waste like food or chemical solutions like paint? the Citizen App can help by with this in two ways (Figure 22):

- **by search:** suggesting a matching term while the user is typing, i.e. tablecloth, “tablecloth (organic waste) or tablecloth (with other components)”
- **on the search result:** when the result is displayed, showing up all the sorting options with a colour tag and a small description

Figure 22. Sort my waste -many options (on search)

When the user types “tablecloth” on the search box and choose i.e. “tablecloth” one of the suggested options the Citizen App displays the result showing up the sorting options details including multiple options to sort this waste according to the right status (condition) of the resource (tablecloth), with a colour tag with a small description like:

Sorting Options

paper	clean tablecloth
biowaste	dirty with only food waste
residual	dirty with other components

Figure 22 shows the case of having many options when querying the sorting of a specific waste.

Figure 23. Sort my waste -many options (on results)

8.3.3 User management

From the left-menu on the right side of the user picture and name will expand the user management options as follows (Figure 24):

- **Account info:** displays the user account information: Full name, citizen card, email, etc. (Figure 25 and Figure 26)
- **Language & location:** allows the user to set the preferred language and enable/disable his/her location information. (Figure 27)
- **Notifications:** to see notifications and to enable/disable the notification preferences (see Section 8.3.10)

Figure 24. User account management options.

Figure 25. User management - Account info

Figure 26. User management - Account info

Figure 27. User management - Language and Location

To check the available notifications and get access to the notification's settings, the user clicks on his/her user account area and then **Notifications**, this will take him/her to the Notifications screen.

8.3.4 Find a Clean Point

When the user needs to search where to sort something special (uncommon waste), for example, an old broken table, he/she clicks on the **Waste Management** option from the left-menu and find the **Find a Clean Point** option included (see Figure 28):

Figure 28. Waste Management: Find a Clean Point option.

After clicking on the **Find a Clean Point** option, the following screen is displayed (see Figure 29), which includes a big map with all available collection centres by default listed the near ones (to the user location) and as previously described for the Deposit Points, a brief information of each Clean Point like address and colour-tag container **clean point** with a plus icon to see the Clean Point details as shown on the Figure 30:

Figure 29. Find a Clean Point.

All sub-level options (included under the main app-option) as Find a Clean Point under Waste Management, are referenced by its image option Waste Management on the right side as follows (Figure 31).

Clicking on the main menu app-option name the app will take the user to its screen. In other words, if the user clicks on Waste Management, they will see the Waste Management screen.

Figure 30. Sublevel options under a menu app-option.

Figure 31. Find a Clean Point -details.

8.3.5 My Behaviour

Every time the citizen needs to check out how is the payments generated from his/her waste management, he/she can click on the **My Behaviour** sub-level option on the **Waste Management** section (see Figure 32):

Figure 32. Waste Management: My Behaviour option.

The **My Behaviour** screen provides a wide information about all payments the citizen has done or will do (real invoice preview) on a specific time according to their waste management.

There are two sections included (Figure 33):

- a **graphical representation** of the waste generation they made, with the specific sorting types and its values.
- **filter options** where the user can choose the specific time range, they need to check (yesterday, current day, week, month, last year, etc.)

Under this interactive area, the application can include some text to help the user to translate the graphical info to a brief explanation. Additionally, a useful tip could be useful too.

Figure 33. Waste Management: My Behaviour.

8.3.6 Global Search

As previously referenced on the Overview of the Citizen App (Section 8.1) the application provides a search tool, "Global Search" always visible and available at the top navbar area of the screen through the search icon which allows the user to make a search all over the information the application manages.

For example, if the user is interested in everything about "organic", this text input on the search box generates some results and the application will provide all content that matches with this term (see Figure 34). Every time the user needs to use this global search will be available for his/her usage as needed.

Figure 34. Global search (from the top navbar).

8.3.7 Filter options

The Citizen App includes a “**Filter by**” button which displays a set of **filter options** the user can customize to display the information according to their needs.

For example, when the app shows up a list of available deposit points, the user can use the filter options to specify if he/she is interested in deposit points in an area of 10 kilometres or specialized about a waste sorting category i.e. oil collection or even if other citizens have made a good or bad review (Figure 35).

The filter options considered are:

- **where:** how far is the deposit point from the current user location
- **category:** what is the waste sorting type (package, glass, paper, etc.)
- **type:** to specify if it is a fixed centre or a mobile point
- **size:** when big or small things are needed to be sort
- **opens at:** work days of the deposit point
- **user reviews:** to filter by choosing the satisfaction of usage from other citizens

With the **apply filters** button to reset it all.

Figure 35. Filter options.

8.3.8 Incentives

The Citizen App provides information about social actions would be the interest of its users (residential and non-residential citizens) like local cooperative initiatives to change their habits and behaviours on the recycling promotion and the waste generation reduction.

To achieve this purpose, the user can get all information about it clicking on the **Incentives** option from the left-menu of the Citizen App (see Figure 36) and all incentives are listed with a descriptive image and brief text with a link to the website where this action is hosted (see Figure 37).

Figure 36. Incentives entry on the left-menu.

Figure 37. Incentives screen.

8.3.9 Best Practices

The Citizen App provides information about best practices from the collaborative prevention actions and products and services from businesses with implemented best practices to optimize the environmental impact about the waste management and the citizen behaviour improvement.

Figure 38. Best Practices entry on the left-menu.

When the user clicks on the **Best Practices for me**, the application displays a list of images from the best practices according to the waste management behaviour of the citizen. For example, if plastic is the most resource sorted by the user, the best practices provided by the app will be about the optimal plastic usage or products and services with a best plastic management and optimization approach.

Other options like **Green Points** can be provided in this Best Practices screen as well (see Figure 39). These green points will be the food banks, sustainable and green areas for recreational activities. For example, if the user clicks on the peppers image, this will flip (rotates) and provide a little description about it including a website URL where more information can be found (see Figure 40 -Figure 42).

Figure 39. Best Practices options screen.

Figure 40. Best Practices for me: choosing one from the list.

Figure 41. Best Practices for me: Best Practice detail.

Figure 42. Best Practices: Green Points.

In addition, users can also populate the best practices database through a form that gather all the required data as seen in (Figure 44-Figure 47).

Figure 43. Best Practices: Economic Activity Mapping.

Figure 44. Best Practices: Economic Activity Mapping. Adding a best practice to a Local Trade.

Figure 45. Best Practices: Economic Activity Mapping. Adding a best practice to a Local Trade (steps).

Figure 46. Best Practices: Economic Activity Mapping. Adding a best practice to a Local Trade (steps).

Figure 47. Best Practices: Upload new best practice.

8.3.10 Notifications

The Citizen App manages a set of messages notify the user something special is happening at that time. When a notification comes, the user has two options to check it out:

- making a click on the bell icon of the top navbar (right side of the screen)
- using the Notifications entry from the User account management > **Notifications**

In any case this will take the user to the Notifications screen (see Figure 48)

Figure 48. User management – Notifications.

When a new notification is available a number will be shown over the bell icon on the top navbar (top right-side area). If the user clicks on it the **Notifications** screen is displayed, showing up all the available notifications, like known issues in the collection system, the status change of the citizen if they raise a new level on the global ranking, the tip of the day or any other relevant message would help the user to be informed about his/her individual waste management or his/her community.

In this screen, clicking on the provided link aside to the message (notification) the user can check the information in detail in the specific screen where this message comes from, i.e. if the notifications are about a change in the nappies container, the link will redirect him/her to the waste management section. Likewise, from here, the user can change the notifications settings according to his/her needs. See the Notifications settings screen in Figure 49.

Figure 49. User management - Notifications settings.

The Notifications settings screen includes all available options to enable/disable messages from the applications about useful information of the waste management in the community, the collection system and special events about waste management. The user can reset to the default notification settings every according to their needs.

8.4 Terms of Use

A special clause for the user to accept (explicitly) the Terms and Conditions of use for the app will be included, following the current regulations on this matter. It will be based on the example provided in Annex B, which is based on the conditions of the Waste App from the Urban Waste project GA No. 690452.

A special clause to inform the users no personal data will be handled will be included. In this App, FDeusto will not be the entity responsible for any process that involves personal data management.

These issues are under review of Waste4Think Ethical Committee.

References

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APPENDIXES OF D4.11 Technical Documentation of R5, R6 and R7: **Apps**

FDEUSTO

Type of document: Report

Dissemination level: Public

Reviewers: UPATRAS, ENBIO, SOFTLINE

Version	Date	Description of main changes	Author
1.0	06/02/2018	First draft	FDEUSTO
1.1	26/10/2018	Second draft (Citizen App & LocalTrade app merged)	FDEUSTO
2.0	29/11/2018	Edited according to reviewers' comments (major edition)	FDEUSTO
2.1	18/12/2018	Final version including reviewers' comments	FDEUSTO

Annex A: Draft of the Terms of Use of the Food App

1. This application is not suitable for people who are allergic or who have any food intolerance.
2. The DONOR COMPANY will not obtain neither economic retribution nor other type of retribution for the delivery to the receiving entity of the food through the FOODAPP. The RECEIVING COMPANY undertakes not to sell or use in any type of transaction the food received through the FOODAPP.
3. The DONOR COMPANY undertakes to always deliver the food in suitable conditions for consumption according to the opinion, where appropriate, of the authorized Health Technical Services. The RECEIVING COMPANY undertakes to keep the food in suitable conditions, paying special attention to the expiration dates and preferential consumption. Both entities are responsible for complying with the cold chain, as well as for complying with all the hygienic and sanitary conditions of food management, the DONOR COMPANY being RESPONSIBLE until the moment of donation. After the donation, the RECEIVING COMPANY undertakes to dispose of and use the administrative and operational capacity required to carry out the free distribution of the food delivered by the donor in optimum conditions and in order to comply with the required storage and cleaning requirements.
4. The truthfulness of the information contained in the FOODAPP concerning the food made available to the RECEIVING ENTITIES is the responsibility of the DONOR ENTITIES.

FDEUSTO, as the entity responsible for the FOODAPP, is not responsible for any damage caused by the poor state of the food derived from the non-observance of the previous commitments.

PRIVACY POLICY

The management of personal data of users will be carried out in the terms provided by the law, including the rights of opposition, access, rectification and cancellation of their personal data, with the user being able to exercise these rights in writing (LETTER, EMAIL ...) addressed to FDEUSTO.

The user data that are essential for the operation of the application will be stored in a file whose responsibility is FDEUSTO.

FDEUSTO will not store any data of FOODAPP users that are not strictly essential for the provision of the Service.

When the FOODAPP is deleted, the data stored in the corresponding file will be destroyed by FDEUSTO.

Annex B: Draft of the Terms of Use of the Citizen App

1. Introduction

These Terms and Conditions shall manage your use of [APP_NAME] Application. These terms will be applied fully and affect to your use of [APP_NAME]. By using this application, you agree to accept all terms and conditions written in here. You must not use this application if you disagree with any of these Terms and Conditions. [APP_NAME] has been developed for the Waste4Think Research Project, under the funding of the EU H2020 program. The Waste4Think Consortium is formed by the partners of this project and the name of the cities, entities, companies and universities and their role can be found at <http://waste4think.eu/>. Minors or people below 18 years old are not allowed to use this application.

2. Intellectual Property rights

Other than the content you own, under these Terms Waste4Think Consortium and/or its licensors own all the intellectual property rights and material contained in this Application. You are granted limited license only for purposes of viewing and using the material contained on this Application.

3. Restrictions

Users are specifically restricted from all the following, at least without a specific permission from the Consortium:

- Publishing any material from this Application in any other media
- Selling, sublicensing and/or otherwise commercializing any application material; publicly performing and/or showing any material from this Application
- Using this application in any way that is or may be damaging the Application itself, or using this Application in any way that impacts user access to this Application
- Using this application contrary to applicable laws and regulations, or in any way may cause harm to the Application, or to any person or business entity
- Engaging in any data mining, data harvesting, data extracting or any other similar activity in relation to this Application; different that specifically admitted by the Waste4Think Consortium
- Using this Application to engage in any advertising or marketing, different than the specifically declared on this EU Research Project

Certain areas of this Application are restricted from being access by users and [Waste4Think Consortium may further restrict access by users to any areas of this Application, at any time, in absolute discretion. Neither confidential data nor data able to grant access to user's identity are acquired, stored or processed. By accepting these Terms and Conditions, user agrees with granting a permission for the installation and use of this Application in a specific device and agrees to allow the Waste4Think Consortium to acquire data regarding location information services on that device.

4. External contents

In these Terms and Conditions, "External Content" shall mean any audio, video, text, images or other material the User choose to display on this Application. [APP_NAME] is neither storing nor supporting displaying these Contents and [Waste4Think Consortium declines all responsibility on this. Waste4Think Consortium reserves the right to remove any Content from any user or participant on this Application at any time without notice. Specifically, no Waste4Think Consortium member, nor any of its officers, directors and employees, can be held liable by this External Contents in terms of legal property or invasion of any third-party's rights.

5. No warranties

This Application is provided "as is", with all faults and Waste4Think Consortium express no representations or warranties, of any kind related to this Application or the materials contained on this Application. Also, nothing contained on this Application shall be interpreted as an advice for the users.

6. Limitation of Liability

In no event shall Waste4Think Consortium members, nor any of its officers, directors and employees, shall be held liable for anything arising out of or in any way connected with your use of this Application whether such liability is under contract. Waste4Think Consortium members, including its officers, directors and employees shall not be held liable for any indirect, consequential or special liability arising out of or in any way related the use of this Application.

7. Indemnification

The user hereby fully indemnifies Waste4Think Consortium from and against any and/or all liabilities, costs, demands, causes of action, damages and expenses arising in any way related to his/her breach of any of the provisions of these Terms.

8. Severability

If any provision of these Terms is found to be invalid under any applicable law, such provisions shall be deleted without affecting the remaining provisions herein.

9. Variation of Terms

The Waste4Think Consortium is permitted to revise these Terms at any time as it sees fit, and by using this Application you are expected to review these Terms on a regular basis.

10. Assignment

The Waste4Think Consortium is allowed to assign, transfer, and subcontract its rights and/or obligations under these Terms without any notification. Any modification on the role or status of the participants on the Consortium can be also performed without any notification to the Users. However, users are not allowed to assign transfer or subcontract any of your right and/or obligations under these Terms.

11. Entire Agreement

These terms constitute the entire agreement between Urban waste consortium and the users in relation to their use of this application and supersede all prior agreements and understanding

12. Governing law & jurisdiction

These terms will be governed by and interpreted in accordance with the law of the Kingdom of Spain, and you submit to the non-exclusive jurisdiction of courts located in Spain for the resolution of any disputes. Specific injuries to contents provided by Waste4Think Consortium members can be also prosecuted under the National Laws of any country where the Application is used.

Comments from external reviewers

External reviewer 1

DATE: 04.12.2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		4	Numbers on figures missing (probably they will be added when the deliverable is finished)
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		X	1	Currently all Figures are not numbered
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		3	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	Minor mistakes
Glossary present in the document?		X	5	All terms are well described, no glossary needed

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External reviewer 2

DATE: 04.12.2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		4	Index of Tables" need to be added
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?		X	4	Few spelling mistakes
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?		X		No glossary needed

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External Reviewer 3

DATE 17.12.2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?		X		All terms are well described, no glossary needed

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